

ESSENTIAL METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR ESP LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores essential methods and techniques for teaching English for Specific Purposes learners. It highlights the importance of a needs-based approach in ESP instruction, emphasizing tailored curriculum design that aligns with learners' professional or academic goals. It examines the integration of authentic materials, technology-enhanced learning, and role-playing activities to enhance learners' practical language skills. The paper also addresses challenges in ESP teaching, such as varying learner proficiency levels and the need for specialized instructor training. The findings suggest that a learner-centred, context-driven approach significantly improves language acquisition and professional communication skills.

Keywords: ESP, methods, language skills, pair work, strategies, functions

English for Specific Purposes refers to the teaching and learning of English language skills for specific academic or professional purposes. Its function is to help learners develop the language skills they need to communicate effectively in specific fields or professions, such as business, engineering, or medicine.

ESP students typically fall into two categories. They are either in higher education and need to use English to study a particular subject or field. Or they are professionals who need to use English in their work, such as doctors, lawyers, or business executives.

As a result, students wanting to study ESP can come from a variety of different linguistic and cultural backgrounds. They can also have vastly different levels of English language proficiency. However, one thing they do have in common is that they all tend to be non-native speakers who are learning English as a second or foreign language.

ESP is all about designing and delivering course material that is tailored to the specific needs of English students in a particular specialized field or profession.

Within an ESP course, ESP lessons generally involve teaching English learners the vocabulary and language used in these specialized fields. So, rather than focusing on teaching grammar and language structures, it concentrates more on language in the context of the specific subject. More general English learning is then integrated within this. This works well because

the goal of ESP is to help learners communicate effectively and accurately in their chosen field or profession using the English language.

A good ESP teacher will try to minimize the negative effects of the learners' emotional reactions to learning and will instead try to boost the positive emotions by using the following strategies:

- Use pair work and group work to minimize the stress of speaking in front of the class, for example, pyramid discussion;
- Structure the task, i.e. introduce the task, remove hurdles, give clear instruction, concept checking, demonstrating the task, run the activity, close the activity and give feedback;
- Give time to think and do, listen to the learners, ask questions, give enough time to think and answer, allow them to complete;
- Emphasis on the process rather than the product as the correct answer is not the most important issue but getting the answer is important;
- Include fun, variations, varieties;
- Avoid monotonous and mechanical teaching.

The Role of the Student The learners come to the ESP class with a specific focus for learning, subject matter knowledge, and well-developed adult learning strategies. They face the task of developing English language skills to reflect their native-language knowledge and skills.

1. **Focus for Learning:** The ESP student has a particular purpose and focus for learning. People learn languages when they have opportunities to understand and work with language in a context that they comprehend and find interesting. ESP is a vehicle for such opportunities. Students will acquire English as they work with materials which they find interesting and relevant and which they can use in their professional work or further studies. Successful learners pay attention to the meaning of the language they hear or read and do not focus primarily on the linguistic input or isolated language structures. The ESP student is particularly well disposed to focus on meaning in the subject-matter field. In ESP, English should be presented not as a subject or body of facts to be learned in isolation from real use, nor as a mechanical skill or habit to be developed. Rather, English should be presented in authentic contexts to acquaint the learners with the particular ways the language is used in functions that they will need to perform in their specialty fields.

2. **Subject-Matter Knowledge:** Learners in the ESP classroom are able to make a real contribution to the language learning process. They are generally aware of the purposes for which they will need to use English. Having already oriented their training toward a specific

field, they see their English instruction as complementing this orientation. Knowledge of the speciality area enables the students to identify a real context for the vocabulary and structures of the ESP classroom. In this way, the learners can take advantage of what they already know about the subject matter field to learn English.

3. Adult Learning Strategies: Learning as an adult has advantages -- adults must work harder than children to learn a new language, but the learning strategies they bring to the task enable them to learn faster and more efficiently. The skills they have already developed in reading and writing their native languages will make learning English easier. Although the English of the students you will be working with will most likely be quite limited, the language learning abilities of the adult in the ESP classroom are potentially great. Language learning continues naturally throughout our lives. Educated adults are constantly learning new language behavior in their native languages; expanding vocabulary, becoming more articulate in their fields, and modifying their linguistic behavior in new situations or new roles. ESP students can tap these natural competencies in learning English.

The role of the teacher In teaching ESP the role of the teacher or ESP practitioner is special, as he or she has to perform five important functions:

- teaching (didactics);
- designing the course, the choice and/or preparation of teaching materials;
- co-operation with academic teachers and/or employers;
- carrying out analyses of the students' needs, target situation and discourse;
- providing an evaluation of the students' progress and an evaluation of the course.

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